

An open source software ecosystem for plasma physics

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Project Summary

Overview

The research team will lead the development of [PlasmaPy](#) and affiliated packages to foster the creation of an open source software ecosystem for plasma physics. The PlasmaPy core package will contain functionality needed by plasma physicists across disciplines, whereas affiliated packages will contain more specialized functionality. At the beginning of the project, the research team will refactor existing code, improve tests, formalize the software architecture, and improve PlasmaPy's base data structures in order to provide a solid foundation for future development. Subsequent code development priorities include a dispersion relation solver for plasma waves and instabilities, the groundwork for a flexible plasma simulation framework, time series turbulence analysis tools, classes for the analysis of plasma diagnostics, and tools to provide access to atomic and physical data. They will make base data structures compatible with open source packages for data science to enable future data science studies. The research team will actively seek input and feedback from the plasma physics community, and adjust code development priorities based on this feedback. The team will hold workshops each year and actively support new users and contributors to grow PlasmaPy into a self-sustaining project.

Intellectual Merit

This effort will significantly improve the scientific reproducibility of plasma physics research by creating a software framework that is open for inspection, modification, and re-use. The team will use best practices for scientific programming to produce highly readable and maintainable code. They will follow the open development model used by highly successful projects like Astropy. They will promote software sustainability by having robust organizational infrastructure, supporting new contributors, and fostering community involvement in multiple ways. The resulting framework will reduce costly duplication of functionality and promote interoperability, including with related software ecosystems in astronomy and heliophysics. This interoperability will allow plasma physics to benefit from functionality developed in other fields. The development roadmap includes functionality that will be useful to broad portions of plasma physics and related disciplines. The proposal team includes members with expertise on laboratory plasma physics, space physics, solar physics, and plasma astrophysics, with representatives from two experimental facilities.

Broader Impacts

An open source software ecosystem will reduce barriers to entry for newcomers to plasma physics by providing clear documentation, access to an active user/developer

community, and an intuitive interface. Such an ecosystem will let students get a head start on their first research projects, as they will no longer need to rewrite functionality that already exists but is hard to read or inadequately documented. Students and scientists will be introduced to collaborative code development practices. Recent plasma graduates who enter industry will have an advantage in the job search if they have experience in Python and collaborative code development. The proposal team will advise numerous students on research projects related to PlasmaPy and affiliated packages. They will create educational materials such as tutorials, Jupyter notebooks, and videos to introduce PlasmaPy alongside core concepts in plasma physics. Documentation will provide an introduction to plasma physics concepts, and will thus be a good place for newcomers to start. The team will prioritize disability access, including by implementing methods to sonify 1D and 2D data using existing open source Python packages. A software ecosystem will reduce the cost and difficulty of establishing new experimental facilities, especially at small colleges. Students using PlasmaPy will have connections to other institutions through the community that naturally develops around an open source software ecosystem. PlasmaPy and affiliated packages have the potential to be applicable to laboratory plasma physics, plasma astrophysics, solar physics, space plasma physics, fusion energy sciences, materials science, plasma chemistry, plasma engineering, plasma medicine, and any other field in which plasma science plays a role. PlasmaPy has adopted a code of conduct to foster a welcoming and inclusive community.

Project Description

1. Introduction

Software is crucial to all areas of modern plasma physics research. Laboratory plasma physicists use software to interpret plasma diagnostics, analyze experimental results, and glean insights using data science techniques. Space scientists use software to interpret in situ observations from our local space environment. Numericists use software to simulate the behavior of laboratory, heliospheric, and astrophysical plasmas. Theoretical plasma physicists use software to derive models and verify results. Educators use software to demonstrate plasma physics concepts to students. Cross-disciplinary research and cross-comparisons between experiment, observation, simulation, and theory all depend heavily on software.

In recent years, researchers in different scientific disciplines such as astronomy, solar physics, and meteorology have developed open source Python packages for their fields. These packages provide essential functionality, frameworks for data analysis and visualization, and educational resources. The [Astropy project](#) is transforming the way scientific research is done in astronomy by making it more open, collaborative, and reproducible ([Astropy Collaboration 2018](#)). The [Astropy core package](#) contains the functionality needed by most astronomers across subfields. [Astropy's affiliated packages](#) contain more specialized functionality. Astropy's Coordination Committee regulates intercompatibility among the core and affiliated packages. **Astropy and its affiliated packages constitute a software ecosystem for astronomy.**

Despite the importance of software, plasma physics currently lacks a community-wide open source software ecosystem. **We propose to develop [PlasmaPy](#), a community-driven open source Python package for plasma physics, into the foundation of an open source software ecosystem for plasma physics research and education.**

2. Motivation

Plasma physics has a “roll your own” culture for code development. Researchers and groups tend to develop software in-house as needed. Most plasma physicists are self-taught programmers. Constant time pressure prevents us from taking the time to learn best practices from computer science. Different researchers and groups often duplicate software with essentially the same functionality. Code tends to be written in a rush to get results that can be published. This code is often directed toward a particular purpose, which makes it more difficult to reuse for other scientific applications. Code contributions are often made without undergoing code review. Documentation tends to be a low priority. Codes with fewer users and developers have fewer people around to find and fix bugs, add features, and provide user support. In-house packages often lack

a testing framework, which can make users reluctant to make changes for fear of unknowingly breaking something somewhere in the code. Different in-house packages lack interoperability with each other, which makes it harder to work with other groups, or even other researchers in the same group. Packages tend to be difficult to install, especially when they depend on external libraries that must be manually compiled and linked.

The combination of all of these factors increases the difficulty of beginning research in plasma physics, collaborating within or across disciplines, and reproducing scientific research. The “roll your own” culture is harmful to students because it imposes significant research overhead, reduces their productivity, isolates them, and prevents them from developing the collaborative code development skills that would be essential if they decide to enter private industry after graduating. And to be frank, it can make research really frustrating.

An open source software ecosystem for plasma physics will allow the plasma physics community to pool resources and enable new research both within and across disciplines. The plasma community has seen the reemergence of fundamental plasma physics research in recent years. New and established user facilities such as the [Basic Plasma Science Facility \(BaPSF\)](#) at UCLA, the [Wisconsin Plasma Physics Laboratory \(WiPPL\)](#) at the University of Wisconsin–Madison, the [Magnetized Plasma Research Laboratory \(MPRL\)](#) at the University of Auburn, and the [Facility for Laboratory Reconnection Experiments \(FLARE\)](#) at Princeton have begun serving as nexuses for cutting-edge research that can be performed by a diverse community. As research costs continue to rise, these sites represent opportunities for accessibility to larger research goals by pooling resources and generating a broad research community. Because each of these facilities has largely developed its own software to interact with experimental data, there has been much duplication of effort and a lack of interoperability. Guest investigators at one facility will have to learn new software and data storage conventions if they are awarded time at a different user facility. It thus becomes unnecessarily difficult to perform the same analysis on data from multiple experiments. Similarly, each plasma simulation code has its own conventions for data storage and representing a problem setup. **A software ecosystem for plasma physics will reduce both costly duplication of functionality and the difficulty of comparing results from different simulations and experiments.**

An open source software ecosystem will broaden access to plasma physics research and education. On top of this new emphasis on user facilities has been an increase in the number of plasma laboratories developed outside plasma flagship institutions. In recent years, many new plasma laboratories have been created at places such as the University of Maryland–Baltimore County, The College of New Jersey, Virginia Tech, the University of Alaska–Anchorage, Washington College, and Bryn Mawr College (host to the [Bryn Mawr Magnetohydrodynamic Experiment; BMX](#)). While

the expansion of plasma research into new and diverse locations is a boon for the community, it comes with its own set of challenges. These institutions can be quite isolated from the broader community and thus lose the connection to common knowledge exchange that happens naturally at flagship plasma institutions with a critical mass of interacting researchers. An open source software ecosystem will provide small colleges and independent researchers with access to tools to perform cutting edge plasma physics research that were developed in collaboration with scientists at flagship plasma institutions. Students at small institutions will be able to interact with plasma scientists at larger institutions via the community that naturally develops around an open source software ecosystem. A package such as PlasmaPy will significantly reduce the code development overhead required to establish small-scale plasma experiments and make it easier to begin research in plasma physics.

An open source software ecosystem will improve the quality and efficiency of plasma physics research. Open source scientific software with an active user/developer community tends to be of higher quality with lower bug densities than closed source scientific software. This is because users are empowered to implement feature requests themselves and submit bug fixes. The use of continuous integration testing reduces the likelihood of bugs finding their way into the code. When bugs are found, new tests can and should be written to make sure that the bug fix holds. The result is code that can be shown to be robust and reliable. Researchers that are able to reuse existing code will not have to spend time unnecessarily repeating what others have written, thus making research more efficient.

PlasmaPy — or something like it — is needed to make plasma research reproducible. Reproducibility is a cornerstone of the scientific method. Results should be able to be reproduced before being broadly accepted. While a survey of scientists found that physicists have high confidence that physics research is reproducible ([Baker 2016](#)), no large-scale studies of the reproducibility of physics have been performed to support or refute this claim. Unfortunately, the scientific reproducibility best practices that are being rapidly adopted in fields like psychology are largely not being adopted in plasma physics ([Murphy et al. 2019c](#)). Data from laboratory plasma experiments and numerical simulations are usually not made publicly available. The software used to analyze data and reach scientific conclusions is rarely released, and is often written in proprietary languages. These closed science practices inhibit reproducibility by making it extremely hard for researchers to replicate results or to reconcile differences between different experiments. **Open source software enables scientific reproducibility by making code available for inspection, modification, and re-use.**

3. An Open Source Software Ecosystem for Plasma Physics

PlasmaPy is a community-driven open source Python package for plasma physics research and education in the early stages of development ([PlasmaPy](#)

[Community 2018b](#)). PlasmaPy development began in earnest in 2017 as a grassroots effort by plasma physics students and scientists who understood the value of an open source software package for our field. In the early stages of the project, contributors wrote a vision statement describing the project's goals; established package infrastructure; chose a permissive open source license; wrote several [PlasmaPy Enhancement Proposals \(PLEPs\)](#) to define organizational structure (see also the Management and Coordination Plan; Murphy [2018a](#), [2018b](#), [2018c](#); [Murphy & Mumford 2018](#)); set up continuous integration testing; wrote extensive documentation; and began development on multiple subpackages.

PlasmaPy v0.1.1 was released last year on the Python Package Index (PyPI) and openly archived on Zenodo ([PlasmaPy Community 2018a](#)). The `atomic` subpackage provides functional and object-oriented interfaces to access properties of atoms, ions, isotopes, and other particles. The `atomic` subpackage is used by most plasma parameter and transport coefficient functions because particle properties such as charge and mass are needed to describe every plasma. The `physics` subpackage contains numerous functions related to plasma parameters and dimensionless quantities. The `mathematics` subpackage contains commonly needed functions such as the plasma dispersion function. The `transport` subpackage contains functionality to calculate plasma transport coefficients using a variety of models. We have begun developing a `diagnostics` subpackage which includes a prototype class for Langmuir probe analysis. The `utils` subpackage contains functionality such as test helper functions. The `classes` subpackage contains the machinery for our base data structures. The goal of the PlasmaPy core package is to provide the functionality that is needed by plasma physicists across disciplines. PlasmaPy affiliated packages will contain more specialized functionality. PlasmaPy currently has one affiliated package under development: [Spectroscopy](#).

At the time of writing, there have been 2273 commits by 44 different contributors to PlasmaPy's main repository, made via 266 merged pull requests. Ten contributors have added more than 1000 lines to the repository. The repository has been forked 111 times and starred 219 times. Our email list has 153 members, including ~50 who signed up in the three hour poster session where the idea for PlasmaPy was first proposed ([Murphy & Huang 2016](#)). PlasmaPy's Matrix group for text-based chat has 83 unique members. A paper recently submitted to the [Plasma 2020 decadal review](#) in support of an open source software ecosystem for plasma physics has 45 different authors and co-signers ([Murphy et al. 2019b](#)). A Plasma 2020 paper in support of an integrated ecosystem of advanced simulation tools for plasma modeling has a completely different 55 authors and co-signers ([Vay et al. 2019](#)). Support has been particularly strong from students and early career scientists. **The plasma physics community recognizes the need for PlasmaPy and is ready for an open source software ecosystem for plasma physics.**

The success of open source scientific software projects depends on a strong community of users and developers in order to scale in the human dimension ([Turk 2013](#)). **We will actively recruit and assist new contributors to grow PlasmaPy into a self-sustaining project** (e.g., [Harihareswara 2017](#)). We will develop a tutorial on how to use PlasmaPy to grow our user community. We will create an additional tutorial on how to make code contributions to empower PlasmaPy users into becoming PlasmaPy developers. We will provide these tutorials while visiting institutions, at conferences, and at PlasmaPy workshops. We will provide these tutorials online at regular intervals. We will support new contributors as they make their first contributions. We will pair program with new contributors at conferences or remotely. We will run live coding exercises online so that new contributors can gain insight into how the development process works. We will continue our practice of creating issues labelled “[good first contribution](#)” so that new contributors have a clear place to start. We will answer questions and provide constructive code reviews quickly. We will maintain and update the development guide we have created in our documentation. Doing these tasks will increase the size of the user and developer communities so that more people are around to answer questions and provide support. As new users and contributors gain experience, we will invite them into becoming subpackage maintainers, members of the Coordinating Committee, and other leadership positions.

We will periodically request open feedback from the plasma physics community about their most pressing software needs and what functionality we should prioritize. We will ask about their standard workflows, what they find most frustrating about research software, and what capabilities would make their lives easier. We will ask what sorts of educational materials using PlasmaPy would be most beneficial as students or instructors. The requests for feedback will take different forms. Our options include sending out an informal questionnaire, publicly calling for feature requests to be raised as issues in PlasmaPy’s repository, hosting town halls at conferences or when visiting institutions, hosting web town halls at regular intervals, and holding open discussions at workshops. We will invite representatives from different experiments and groups to attend our annual workshops. We will use the resulting information to adjust our priorities and improve our code development roadmap.

Codes of conduct are vital for all software collaborations. The [PlasmaPy Community Code of Conduct](#) is derived from the [Contributor Covenant](#) and the [Astropy Community Code of Conduct](#). We chose this code of conduct because it calls not just for a harassment-free space but also for community members to take positive actions to foster a welcoming and inclusive environment. For instance, during code review we strive to provide friendly and constructive feedback and to actively express gratitude and appreciation for the contributions that people are making. When helping someone learn, we try to avoid describing tasks as “easy” or that we “just” do something because these words often unintentionally come across as dismissive (a lesson learned from

[Software Carpentry](#)). As our community grows, we will expand our code of conduct enforcement policies to be more suitable for a large project than a small project.

We will use best practices for scientific programming to produce readable, reliable, and maintainable code; promote software sustainability; and enable scientific reproducibility (Wilson et al. [2014](#), [2017](#); Scopatz & Huff; Martin 2009, 2018; Hettrick 2016; [Wilkinson et al. 2016](#)). We will prioritize readability in order to produce code that is easier to debug, maintain, extend, and maintain. We will design our [application programming interface \(API\)](#) to be simple, intuitive, and user-friendly. We will choose variable names that are descriptive: a name like `gyroradius` is more physically intuitive than `Larmor_radius`. Every code contribution proposed through a pull request will undergo constructive code review before being merged. We will use exception handling and provide useful error and warning messages. We will optimize code only after it works correctly and only when needed. We describe many of these practices in the development guide in [PlasmaPy's online documentation](#).

PlasmaPy will continue to be well-tested. PlasmaPy has an extensive test suite that is run by [Travis CI](#) and [AppVeyor](#) every time a pull request is made or updated. Similarly, [CircleCI](#) runs a test build of our documentation. We use [Codecov](#) to check which lines of code are covered by tests and which are not. Presently $\approx 96.5\%$ of code in PlasmaPy is covered by at least one test. When we contribute new functions and classes, we will contribute tests. We will test that exceptions are raised and warnings are issued as they should be. We will turn bugs into test cases. We will use code coverage information to design tests to cover untested sections of code, find hidden bugs, and identify unused sections of code. We will use code review to check that the quality of test code is as high as the quality of production code.

We will write documentation to be useful for both experienced researchers and students beginning their first research projects in plasma physics. [PlasmaPy's documentation](#) is built automatically and hosted by [Read the Docs](#). We will include traditional documentation in the form of a docstring at the beginning of user-facing functions, classes, and methods. We will create narrative functionality and tutorials to serve as educational resources that can provide more introductory material and context. This approach will make PlasmaPy useful to experienced researchers without getting bogged down in introductory material while providing a firm starting point for newcomers to the field. This approach will also make PlasmaPy more adaptable by the broader physics community (including by individual researchers, for undergraduate plasma laboratory series, and for established plasma facilities).

We will make PlasmaPy interoperable with the existing software ecosystem for astronomy and the emerging software ecosystem for heliophysics. PlasmaPy uses [astropy.units](#) to create [Quantity](#) objects with physical units, which promotes interoperability with Astropy, SunPy ([SunPy Collaboration 2015](#)), and their affiliated

packages. PlasmaPy is an active member of the [Python in Heliophysics Community \(PyHC\)](#) which began in 2018 with support from NASA as an effort to foster interoperability, coordinate development, and reduce unnecessary duplication among ≥ 28 open source heliophysics packages ([Burrell et al. 2018](#); [Ware et al. 2019](#)). Participating projects include [SunPy](#), [SpacePy](#), [HelioPy](#), [pySPEDAS](#), [pysat](#), [fiasco](#), and [ndcube](#). The first PyHC meeting resulted in community code development standards and plans to consolidate [CDF](#) readers and download tools. We will continue to be an active member of PyHC because of how fundamental plasma physics is to heliophysics. Probable areas of collaboration include access to atomic data; spectroscopy, non-equilibrium ionization modeling; fluid and particle-in-cell simulations; analysis of particle distribution functions; time series analyses for turbulent plasmas; and analysis of waves, shocks, reconnection, and turbulence. **Intercompatibility between PlasmaPy and heliophysics Python packages will enable cross-disciplinary studies between heliophysicists and laboratory plasma physicists to investigate the same physical processes in different environments with the same set of tools.** If this proposal is successful, we will emulate PyHC in plasma physics.

4. Code Development Roadmap

The tasks in this section represent major priorities in PlasmaPy's current code development roadmap.¹ During the first few months, we will refactor existing packages and improve the testing framework. These two tasks will solidify the foundation of the package, reduce [technical debt](#),² improve maintainability, and give us a chance to start formalizing software architecture. We will prioritize code development activities based on community input and feedback.

4.1. Refactoring existing code

A common scientific code development practice is to prioritize adding new features while making few improvements to existing code. The disadvantage of this approach is that it allows technical debt to accumulate, especially when new code depends on fragile existing code. Some technical debt does exist in PlasmaPy, especially for early contributions to the project before our development practices were codified. At the beginning of this project, the proposal team will undergo a period of code review and refactoring in order to reduce the amount of technical debt. We will: (1) improve decorators for plasma parameter calculations responsible for exception handling; (2) implement improved tools from the `atomic` subpackage into the plasma parameter calculations; (3) make the class responsible for the calculation of transport coefficients

¹ We do not include code development activities solely related to fusion energy sciences (FES) because such tasks are traditionally funded by DOE rather than NSF. However, we will coordinate with and provide user support to members of the FES community, including those who wish to develop affiliated packages.

² Technical debt is described as the result of taking an easy approach to enable quick progress instead of a robust approach that will make the code more reliable and maintainable in the long term.

less monolithic; (4) improve the representation of dielectric tensor components; (5) fill in gaps in the documentation such as missing docstrings; (6) remove implicit particle assumptions in `physics` and `transport` functions; and (7) go through the backlog of issues that have been raised on GitHub. This period of refactoring will improve code quality, provide a strong foundation for future code development, and give an opportunity for the newer contributors on our team to learn about the package structure and our development practices.

4.2. Improving tests and testing capabilities

Test code is equally as important as production code (Martin 2009). Test suites that are absent or hastily written act as change preventers. If a test suite is difficult to read or modify, programmers may avoid altering production code to avoid the frustration of updating poorly written tests. Modifying code without tests risks introducing hidden bugs with no practical way of tracking them down (e.g., Feathers 2005). A high quality testing framework makes production code more flexible since we can make changes without fear of introducing hidden bugs. The quality of tests written during PlasmaPy development has increased with time as we began implementing improved testing strategies that we learned from the broader open source community. As we refactor existing functionality, we will improve the tests that were written early in the project. Our specific tasks will be to: (1) refactor and generalize test helper functions; (2) apply test helper functions to the `physics` and `transport` subpackages; (3) improve the clarity of error messages; and (4) implement [pytest.fixture](#) and class-based tests as appropriate.

4.3. Formalizing software architecture

As we refactor existing code and improve tests, we will begin the process of formalizing the software architecture of PlasmaPy using lessons from computer science (e.g., Martin 2018). We will create a dependency diagram for the development guide so that we can avoid circular dependencies. We will minimize multiple inheritance (Wasserman 1990). We will create and enforce boundaries between different software components, and make sure that each module has a single responsibility. We will engage in best practices such as keeping established components of software open for extension but closed for modification (Meyer 1988), making sure that subclasses can always be used in place of their parent classes ([Liskov 1988](#)), avoiding dependencies on functionality that is not actually needed, and not having high level functionality depend directly on low level details. We will use the architectural framework that we create as the foundation of the expanded framework. We will restructure our documentation around this framework to provide newcomers with an overall view of PlasmaPy. As we begin to add new functionality, we will build upon and adapt PlasmaPy's architectural model.

4.4. High level data structures

One of the most fundamental design decisions for PlasmaPy is how to represent different plasmas. This decision is challenging given that plasma data comes from many different sources (simulations, laboratory measurements, in situ spacecraft observations, and analytical representations) in many different formats (e.g., [NetCDF](#), [MDSplus](#), and [HDF5](#)) with many different conventions for storing and representing metadata.

The first option we considered was to create a single `Plasma` class that includes all of the data and methods for all forms and formats. Users would only need to interact with a single class with a unique API, but this monolithic class would very quickly become very unwieldy. The second option we considered was to create distinct classes for each form and/or format. Each class would then be leaner, but there would likely be repeated code and the different classes will likely end up with different APIs. Neither of these approaches was satisfactory. We finally decided to take a hybrid approach and define an abstract base class to broadly represent plasmas in general (see PLEP 6; [Leonard 2018](#)). The abstract base class will define abstract methods that must be defined in each subclass. We then subclass that abstract base class in order to represent particular types of plasmas. The abstract base class will define abstract methods that must be defined by each subclass, thus enforcing API consistency between different subclasses. Subclasses will have the freedom to include additional methods and attributes when necessary. We use the `Plasma` “class factory” (based on [SunPy’s Map class factory](#)) which will select and instantiate the appropriate subclass based on the provided arguments. Users then need only recall one mechanism for instantiating classes for different data types. PlasmaPy’s [Google Summer of Code](#) student in 2018 implemented the machinery for this approach ([Malhotra 2018](#)) and created the first subclass for the [openPMD](#) standard ([Huebl et al. 2017](#)).

We will continue to develop our base data structures throughout this project. The design of the base data structures must be iterative: we will adjust the API and add methods based on user feedback. We will implement high level methods to analyze and visualize plasma configurations such as 3D magnetic topology or quasi-separatrix layer maps. We will separate high level and low level functionality with abstract interfaces so as to make the methods more general and more reusable. For example, a magnetic field line tracer should depend on a function that returns the value of the magnetic field at a particular location but not depend directly on the details of accessing and interpolating the magnetic field from a data file.

We will develop subclasses of the abstract base class for different data types in response to requests from the community. We will prioritize the implementation of subclasses for open standards, output from open source simulation software, and open access datasets. In order to preserve our ability to change the API, we will prioritize a

small number of subclasses in the first year of this project. We anticipate that the overall class hierarchy will also evolve; for example, we may need different abstractions for fluid and kinetic representations of plasmas.

4.5. Dispersion relation solver

When a plasma in equilibrium is perturbed, it develops different waves and instabilities depending on various parameters. The normal modes of plasma are generally described by a frequency vs. wavenumber relation called the dispersion relation. For a given model, the dispersion or instability relations depend on parameters such as plasma beta, anisotropies for different species, mass ratios, and angles of propagation. The nature of waves and instabilities depends significantly on the physics included in the model. Waves in single fluid magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) differ from when anisotropic and/or kinetic effects are included.

We will implement general-purpose dispersion relation solvers in PlasmaPy. We will design an API where the plasma declaration is done independently before being passed to a particular model. There are many dispersion relation solvers that are available for different programming languages, though these currently lack interoperability. [PDRF \(Xie 2014\)](#) and [PDRK \(Xie & Xiao 2014\)](#) are dispersion relation solvers written in MATLAB for multi-fluid and kinetic models, respectively. [NHDS \(Verscharen & Chandran 2018\)](#) and WHAMP are fully kinetic, multi-species dispersion relation solvers written in Fortran and/or MATLAB. We will port PDRF to Python for implementation in PlasmaPy, and implement a Python interface to NHDS that if possible does not require users to have a Fortran compiler. As time permits, we will port NHDS and/or PDRK functionality into PlasmaPy. We will optimize code as necessary.

4.6. Plasma simulation framework

Numerical simulation is a powerful research tool that allows us to investigate plasma phenomena such as disruptions in tokamaks, solar eruptions, geomagnetic substorms, and accretion into black holes. Simulations can be used to interpret experiments and also serve as a bridge between laboratory, heliospheric, and astrophysical plasma research. A software ecosystem for plasma physics must include a flexible plasma simulation framework.

Most plasma simulation codes are written in compiled languages such as Fortran and C. These languages offer excellent performance, but code development is much slower because these languages are not interactive and types must be declared. Parallelization with [MPI](#) often requires intermixing low-level routines to transfer data with high-level calls related to the numerical method. This intermixing often acts as a change preventer because it makes the numerical method harder to revise. Simulation codes often lack clear boundaries between different components. Access to many of these codes is restricted, especially within the laboratory plasma physics and fusion energy sciences

communities. Codes tend to be hard to install, especially when the documentation is insufficient or external libraries must be compiled and linked. Different codes usually have different conventions for defining initial conditions, boundary conditions, and other aspects of the problem setup. If a researcher wishes to change to a different numerical method or physical model, they must often set up the same problem in an entirely different code from scratch.

We propose to develop the building blocks of a flexible plasma simulation framework for the PlasmaPy ecosystem. As an interpreted language, Python itself is not well-suited to high performance computing. Extensions like [Cython](#) are cumbersome to work with, and [just-in-time \(JIT\) compilation](#) with [Numba](#) is not well-suited to massively parallel applications. Using Python to call code written in Fortran or C is common, but code development in these languages is slow and [metaprogramming](#) capabilities at runtime are limited. [Julia](#) is a new high-level interactive dynamically typed language that synthesizes the best features of C, Python, Ruby, Perl, R, MATLAB, and Lisp for scientific computing. Julia uses JIT compilation with [type inference](#) and [multiple dispatch](#) to achieve performance comparable to C and Fortran, even without type declarations ([Bezanson et al. 2017](#)). Julia can be run interactively. Julia natively supports parallelization and has reached petascale ([Regier et al. 2019](#)). These features greatly speed up code development and optimization by allowing prototyping in the same language used for performance runs. [Julia can be called from Python](#) and [Python can be called from Julia](#), so these two languages can coexist in a single ecosystem. We will develop our core simulation capabilities in Julia and design it to be used with or without a Python interface.

We will develop abstract interfaces to enable different problem setups, physical models, and numerical methods to be decoupled from each other. We will develop a standard for representing the problem setup independently of the physical model and numerical method. This standard will include specifications for the initial/boundary conditions and computational domain. Creating such a boundary with an abstract interface will provide a clear separation of responsibility between the problem specification and the numerics. We will develop abstract interfaces for numerical methods, physical models, and simulation results. These abstractions will allow users to write the same high level code without depending on the details hidden in the abstraction. We will coordinate with the creators of the [Particle-In-Cell Modeling Interface \(PICMI\)](#). We will develop these interfaces with enough generality so that they can be used with codes developed by other groups. We will develop these interfaces iteratively by starting with simple setups and numerical methods and increase complexity as the interface stabilizes.

The scope of this effort has the potential to be immense, so we must carefully prioritize code development activities. **We will prioritize numerical methods that can be separated from the system of equations, as can often be done for conservation**

laws (LeVeque 1992). The spectral element method described by [Lukin et al. \(2016\)](#) and used in the [HiFi framework](#) is highly suitable as a prioritized numerical method. This high order implicit method solves arbitrary systems of equations written in [conservative form](#). Users specify the flux and source terms, and may change them to change the system of equations. [Spectral and finite element methods](#) are widely used for simulating laboratory experiments with a realistic computational domain due to their geometric flexibility (e.g., [Murphy & Sovinec 2008](#)) and excellent convergence properties. This method is particularly well-suited for implementation in Julia because of metaprogramming capabilities unavailable in Fortran: we could let users specify flux and source terms as strings that could be processed to create functions that can be compiled at runtime with the JIT compiler. A Julia implementation will also allow us to benefit from [automatic differentiation](#) (e.g., Rall 1981) capabilities provided by the [ForwardDiff](#) and [ReverseDiff](#) packages so users need not manually input all of the terms needed to calculate the Jacobian matrix.

The goal of this effort is not to finish a complete framework for plasma simulations, but rather to lay a strong foundation that can be built upon by future researchers and in future projects. If time permits, we will implement additional numerical methods such as particle-in-cell (PIC) simulation capabilities; visualization tools; and methods to create synthetic diagnostics using the classes described below. [We are writing PLEP 7](#) to describe longer-term goals of this effort (with use cases, software requirements specifications, draft architectural design, and suggested tests).

4.7. Experimental data analysis

PlasmaPy must have an experimental analysis package to connect to the laboratory plasma physics community. PlasmaPy gives our community the unique opportunity to develop robust diagnostic analysis tools that are reviewed by a diverse community base and tested against a wide parameter space. This effort will provide better transfer of knowledge from one generation of science to the next and promote a faster and more consistent analysis cycle. Our goals in this effort are to: (1) provide a comprehensive set of classes for analyzing data collected by commonly deployed plasma diagnostics; and (2) creating documentation that covers class functionality, provides educational information about each diagnostic, and describes how members of the plasma community can develop classes for diagnostics themselves. We will develop a universal diagnostic class structure to provide a consistent and predictable user interface, an intuitive diagnostics configuration interface, and an easily subclassed structure that users can tailor to their needs.

We will develop base classes for the most commonly used plasma diagnostics in the first and second years: [Langmuir probes](#) (including swept probes, triple probes, double probes, and Mach probes) and magnetic flux (b-dot) probes. During later years, we will add analysis classes for emissive probes, velocity analyzers, spectroscopy (in

partnership with the solar and astronomy community), interferometry, Thomson scattering, laser-induced fluorescence, and additional community-requested diagnostics. We will prioritize the development of diagnostic classes based on community demand, feasibility, and diversity. Our goal is to cover the analysis needs of various sectors of the plasma community: from laboratory plasma physics to in situ spacecraft measurements to high energy density physics (HEDP). When a diagnostic has applications in multiple disciplines, we will reach out to these different communities to improve reliability, avoid overlap, and enable interoperability. If time permits, we will develop graphical user interfaces (GUIs) for diagnostic analyses, which would be especially useful for diagnostics like Thomson scattering and spectroscopy.

We will make each diagnostic class intuitively configurable for the properties of that diagnostic (e.g., number of sensing elements, active sensing area, probe geometry, supporting electronic configuration) and easily subclassable for any unique purpose needed by the user. We will validate each diagnostic class with physical probe measurements over a wide parameter space. Validation and benchmarking will be done with diagnostic measurements taken during experimental campaigns at BaPSF and BMX. These benchmark datasets will be a combination of archival datasets and new measurements. The class results will be benchmarked against existing in-house analysis codes. We will reach out to the broader community for input and sample data for diagnostics and parameter regimes not feasible at BaPSF or BMX.

Documentation on the `diagnostics` subpackage will be written so that users may learn about a diagnostic's theory, construction, and data analysis techniques. We will develop both written and video tutorials so that users can practice apply data analysis techniques in PlasmaPy to real world sample data and create their own diagnostic classes.

4.8. Time series turbulence analysis

Plasmas ranging from Earth's magnetosheath to laboratory experiments are frequently observed to be in a turbulent state. Various statistical properties are used to categorize and understand turbulence in different systems. Such properties include power spectra, probability distribution functions (PDFs), scale-dependent kurtosis, and energy decay rates. These diagnostics are useful to quantify the dynamics of turbulent fluctuations. Because of the importance of turbulence in essentially all subfields of plasma physics, we will implement tools to analyze the properties of turbulence for simulation results, time series obtained from spacecraft, and laboratory experiments. Time series analysis will be implemented using `pandas`. We will (1) use a package from PyHC to import datasets from multiple spacecraft, convert these datasets to a format consistent with the rest of PlasmaPy, and create time series; (2) implement statistical analysis functionality such as PDFs of increments, joint PDFs of various variables, scale-dependent kurtosis, structure functions, correlation functions, and decay rates; (3) create similar functionality

for analyzing simulation datasets; and (4) create tutorials that download archival datasets and reproduce published plots. We will provide equivalent codes to reproduce published results from simulations using our existing datasets.

4.9. Enabling data science studies

Over the last few years, the emerging field of data science (e.g., [Spears et al. 2018](#)) has begun to be applied to plasma physics research. Machine learning applications in plasma physics include prediction of transport, instabilities, and disruptions in tokamaks (e.g., [Smith et al. 2016](#); [Meneghini et al. 2017](#); [Rea et al. 2018](#)), closures for models of turbulence (Tracey et al. 2015), and predicting yields resulting from inertial confinement experiments (Nora et al. 2017). The range of potential applications for data science to plasma physics is extremely broad. The purpose of a package like PlasmaPy is to provide the building blocks to be used by other researchers in data science applications. We will accomplish this by making our data structures compatible with [scikit-learn](#) and providing examples of data science techniques.

The application of data science techniques to laboratory plasma physics using data from different sources is hindered by several barriers. The first barrier is that experimental data is usually closed access. Prospective researchers must often agree to restrictions on the use and redistribution of the data, which hampers scientific reproducibility. We will address this barrier by developing a unified interface for users to query and download open access plasma datasets (such as from BMX) that become available online.³ This interface will complement existing tools for heliophysics and astronomy. The second barrier is that different experiments have different conventions for recording metadata, data provenance, and other vital information. Accurate interpretation of data often requires direct consultation with an expert on the diagnostic that provided the data. We will address this barrier by providing a common interface to analyze data from different experiments and by working with experimentalists to establish open metadata standards for experimental results. The third barrier is that laboratories tend to use custom in-house software. This barrier increases the difficulty of comparing results from an experiment with other experiments or in situ data. This barrier will be addressed naturally through developing an open source software ecosystem for plasma physics. Our goal is for plasma physics data and software to be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable ([FAIR](#); e.g., [Wilkinson et al. 2016](#)).

4.10. A unified interface to atomic and physical data

We will develop functionality to access atomic data commonly needed by plasma physicists. Such atomic data include ionization/recombination rates, cross sections for

³ In a community paper submitted to the Plasma 2020 decadal review on making plasma research reproducible, we strongly advocate for funding agencies to foster the creation of a universal portal for access to online plasma datasets ([Murphy et al. 2019c](#)) akin to the [Virtual Solar Observatory](#).

a variety of atomic processes, fusion reaction rates, and collisional/radiative excitation rates. These data are available from numerous databases, including many that are available online. However, some databases are more appropriate for astronomers (who may care more about forbidden transitions) while others are more important for experimentalists (who may care more about atomic rates for tungsten). We will include functionality to access atomic data from multiple databases in coordination with PyHC. The most commonly needed data will be stored in the main package; other data will be accessed using query tools.

4.11. Addressing community needs

PlasmaPy development is by no means limited to the key priorities described above. We will implement or help members of the plasma physics community implement additional features such as Grad-Shafranov plasma equilibrium solvers using multiple methods; stability analysis tools; general purpose utilities such as getting the current density from the magnetic field or magnetic field from the vector potential; plasma parameter and transport functions for dusty, relativistic, high energy density, and partially ionized plasmas; classes to represent shocks and equilibria; coordinate transformations; a Biot-Savart law solver; and magnetic topology visualization tools. Functionality can be requested by [creating issues on PlasmaPy's GitHub repository](#). We will prioritize development of additional features based on community needs.

5. Intellectual Merit

Our effort will make plasma physics research more reproducible by creating a software framework that is open for inspection, modification, and reuse. The adoption of best practices for scientific programming will result in code that is more readable and maintainable. We will promote software sustainability by having a well-defined organizational infrastructure, involving the community in multiple ways, providing guidance and support to new contributors, releasing sufficient documentation (including a code development guide), making our software products citable and discoverable (see also the Data Management Plan), creating educational resources that depend on PlasmaPy, hosting tutorials and workshops, and fostering a welcoming and inclusive environment. A software ecosystem for plasma physics will reduce costly duplication of functionality and promote interoperability. We will coordinate with related efforts such as PyHC and Astropy to enable greater interoperability and cross-disciplinary collaboration. Plasma physics will then be able to benefit from tools and software infrastructure being developed by and for other fields. We are designing our base data structures to maintain a consistent API between different subclasses while providing for flexibility in representing disparate datasets. We will develop our base data structures to be compatible with `scikit-learn` to enable data science studies. Our development roadmap includes features that will be useful to broad portions of plasma physics and

related disciplines, including dispersion relation solvers, time series turbulence analysis, atomic data access, and plasma diagnostic analysis. We will develop the foundation of a plasma simulation framework, and use abstract interfaces to decouple the problem setup from the numerics. We will prioritize code development activities based on community feedback and input. The proposal team includes members with expertise on laboratory plasma physics, space physics, solar physics, plasma astrophysics, and open source scientific software development, as well as representatives from two experimental facilities. **A software ecosystem for plasma research and education is a sound investment for plasma physics and related communities with very tangible benefits and few drawbacks that will reduce the time, effort, and frustration needed to reach scientific understanding.**

6. Broader Impacts

We will advise students on projects related to PlasmaPy during all five years. Sample projects could include implementation of a numerical method or synthetic diagnostics in the plasma simulation framework, application of diagnostic classes for validation against experiments, or developing and development of a fluid plasma dispersion relation solver. These students will come from the home institutions of the research team as well as other colleges and universities. We will advertise internships through the [National Society of Black Physicists](#); [Conferences for Undergraduate Women in Physics](#); American Astronomical Society (AAS) [Working Group on Accessibility and Disability \(WGAD\)](#); [Society for Advancement of Chicanos, Hispanics, and Native Americans in Science](#); and/or physics departments at Historically Black Colleges and Universities with programs in plasma physics.

An open source software ecosystem will reduce barriers to entry for newcomers to plasma physics by providing clear documentation, access to an active user/developer community, and an intuitive interface. Such an ecosystem will let students get off to a fast start when beginning their first research projects. This ecosystem will reduce the need to rewrite functionality that already exists but is hard to read, inadequately documented, or closed source. A common analysis framework provides opportunities for new researchers (primarily undergraduates) outside of flagship plasma institutions to access common analysis techniques without the benefit of having a plasma physics courses. Through PlasmaPy, undergraduates will be able to learn how to perform common plasma physics analysis techniques. Such a broader audience can help shift the current diversity trends seen in the plasma community. Students and scientists will be introduced to collaborative code development practices that are widely used in industry. Experience in Python and collaborative code development will provide recent graduates who enter industry with a job search advantage. The PlasmaPy code of conduct calls for positive actions to foster a welcoming and inclusive environment.

We will develop educational materials for plasma physics. We will write documentation to provide a solid introduction to the parameter, technique, diagnostic, or numerical method in question. We will create tutorials, [Jupyter](#) notebooks, and videos to introduce plasma physics topics along with corresponding functionality in PlasmaPy. We will design these materials to be able to be used in undergraduate and/or graduate plasma coursework.

PlasmaPy will reduce the cost of developing new experimental facilities. New devices will benefit from not having to invest as much time and resources into software development overhead if they have access to an open source framework for experimental analysis. This benefit will be greatest at small institutions and institutions with limited resources. Students will benefit from having access to and learning from plasma physicists at other institutions by participating in the PlasmaPy community.

We will co-lead or facilitate ~1–2 [Software Carpentry](#) workshops per year at institutions with undergraduate or graduate programs in plasma physics. These workshops will introduce students and scientists to tools that make our lives as researchers easier but are often neglected in coursework. Topics will include Python, version control, and shell scripting.

We will prioritize accessibility for students and scientists with disabilities. We will implement practices recommended by the [Web Accessibility in Mind \(WebAIM\)](#) consortium for PlasmaPy’s online documentation and website. We will improve screen reader friendliness of online materials by linearizing content for better navigation and by including alt-text/captions for images. We will implement [MathJax Accessibility extensions](#) for online documentation. We will write documents (including this proposal) using dyslexic-friendly sans serif fonts. Videos posted online will all have accurate captions. We will make source code more accessible by using pronounceable and descriptive object names. We will develop methods to sonify 1D and 2D data using openly available Python packages such as [mingus](#) in cooperation with WGAD.

7. Work Plan

In this section, we describe our work plan over the five years of this project. Investigator responsibilities are described in the Management and Coordination Plan. This timeline will be adjusted so that we may effectively address community needs. We will support new users, mentor students, hold tutorials, host workshops, make official releases, coordinate with PyHC, develop educational materials, and engage in constructive code reviews during every year.

In **year 1**, we will refactor existing functionality, improve tests, begin formalizing software architecture, expand base data structures, write a PLEP to plan experimental analysis tools, begin development of a universal `Diagnostics` class structure, develop

Langmuir probe classes (focusing on swept and triple probes), and submit an article for publication on PlasmaPy.

In **year 2**, we will implement a fluid dispersion relation solver, create abstract interfaces for the simulation framework, expand the Langmuir probe class to include double probes and Mach probes, create b-dot probe classes, and create tools for access to online plasma datasets.

In **year 3**, we will implement a kinetic dispersion relation solver, add spectral element simulation capabilities, and add one or two new diagnostic classes to be decided based on community needs. These new diagnostics will probably be selected from interferometry, velocity analyzers, and/or spectroscopy. We will submit an article for publication on PlasmaPy.

In **year 4**, we will begin implementing time series turbulence analysis tools, add more diagnostics classes based on community demand (most likely selected from the remainder of the year 3 list, along with emissive probes and Thomson scattering), develop functionality to create synthetic diagnostics from the simulation framework, implement methods to sonify 1D and 2D data, and begin implementing tools to access atomic data in coordination with PyHC.

In **year 5**, we will complete the implementation of time series turbulence analysis tools, add one or two new diagnostic classes (most likely selected from the remainder of the year 4 list), and submit an article for publication on PlasmaPy. We will expand the framework for plasma simulation, analysis, and visualization; create GUIs for plasma diagnostics; and expand access to atomic datasets as time permits and as requested by the plasma community.

8. Results from Prior NSF Support

Dr. Murphy is a co-PI of a SHINE grant on non-equilibrium ionization (NEI) modeling in numerical simulations of solar eruptions (*Exploring Time-Dependent Ionization in Magnetic Reconnection During Solar Eruptions*, \$359,537, AGS-1723313, 9/1/2017–8/31/2020, PI: Chengcai Shen). Dr. Parashar was co-PI of a SHINE grant to study the nature of turbulent fluctuations between proton and electron scales (Short-Wavelength Turbulence in the Solar Wind, \$297,971, AGS-1460130, 4/6/2015–3/31/2019, PI: S. Peter Gary). Dr. Schaffner has no prior NSF support but will be PI of a future NSF grant to establish the Bryn Mawr Plasma Laboratory (*CAREER: The Bryn Mawr Plasma Laboratory—A Liberal-Arts Centered Facility for Basic Plasma Research and Plasma Science Education*, PHY-1846943, 8/15/2019–7/31/2024). Dr. Vincena is co-PI of an NSF grant supporting BaPSF (*Basic Plasma Science Facility Renewal*, \$1,500,000, NSF PHY-1561912, 8/15/2016–7/31/2021, PI: Troy Carter).

8.1. Intellectual merit resulting from prior NSF support

Dr. Murphy co-developed an open source Python package to enable NEI modeling of heliospheric and astrophysical plasmas. This package was successfully used by a student to model ionization state evolution of plasma in a simulation of the solar wind ([Shen et al. 2017](#)) and compared the results to Ulysses charge state observations.

Dr. Parashar and collaborators found that kinetic effects modify the nature of wave-packet collisions and thus the nature of turbulence behind the wave packets (Pezzi et al. [2017a](#), [2017b](#), [2017c](#)), that heating in collisionless plasmas is well described by the pressure strain interaction (Yang et al. 2017a, 2017b; Chasapis et al. 2018), and that relative heating of protons and electrons depends on the amplitude of large scale fluctuations such that large amplitude turbulence at the outer scale heats protons more ([Gary et al. 2016](#); Matthaeus et al. 2016; Hughes et al. 2017).

As the first national user facility for the study of fundamental plasma physics, BaPSF has made possible many contributions to frontier-plasma physics experiments and supporting theoretical and computational efforts. Twenty-eight publications have resulted from this funding period for BaPSF on topics including: whistler waves (Xin et al. 2017; [Van Compernelle et al. 2016](#)); collisionless, shocks (Bondarenko et al. [2017a](#), [2017b](#); Hueur et al. [2017](#), 2018; [Schaeffer et al. 2017](#); Weidl et al. [2016](#), [2017](#)); plasma explosions ([Bonde 2018](#); [Bonde et al. 2018](#)); reconnection ([DeHaas et al. 2017](#); [Gekelman et al. 2018a](#)); transport ([Fisher & Rogers 2017](#); [Poulos & Morales 2016](#); [Poulos 2019](#)); nonlocal properties ([Gekelman et al. 2017](#); [Maggs & Morales 2019](#)); flows ([Jin et al. 2019](#)); time-domain structures ([Gekelman et al. 2018b](#)); thermal waves ([Karbashewski et al. 2018](#); [Morales 2018](#); [Zhao & Morales 2018](#)); fast wave convective cells ([Martin et al. 2017](#)); flux rope topology ([Prior & Yeates 2018](#)); electron acceleration ([Schroeder et al. 2017](#)); nonlinear convection (Sydora et al. 2017); and plasma avalanches ([Van Compernelle et al. 2017](#)).

8.2. Broader impacts resulting from prior NSF support

Dr. Murphy co-advised an undergraduate summer intern who performed the NEI models and made the comparisons to *Ulysses* observations. This student presented his results at a meeting of the AAS. The [NEI code](#) is openly available for use in research and education and is [being incorporated into the PlasmaPy ecosystem](#). Dr. Murphy co-authored a [guide on improving accessibility of astronomical publications](#) that was provided to editorial staff for AAS journals.

Dr. Parashar mentored graduate students, served as a judge for student poster competitions at the AGU and SHINE conferences, and released the [TurbPlasma](#) open source Python package.

The BaPSF grant has helped grow the plasma physics community. In the current award period, six graduate students received their doctoral degrees from their work performed

at BaPSF. BaPSF is a unique mid-scale facility that allows researchers from around the country and internationally to pursue plasma research beyond the scale of single-PI grants. The [bapsflib](#) package was developed as part of this funding by Dr. Erik Everson as a free tool for BaPSF users from the solar, magnetospheric, fusion, low-temperature, and basic plasma communities.

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Management and Coordination Plan

1. Team Member Roles and Responsibilities

Dr. Nicholas Murphy will coordinate the activities described in this proposal and determine which development tasks (except for experimental analysis capabilities) should be prioritized based on community feedback and in partnership with PlasmaPy's Coordinating Committee. He will have primary responsibility for formalizing PlasmaPy's software architecture, leading the refactoring effort, improving the testing framework, developing the numerical simulation framework, and developing or incorporating tools to provide straightforward access to atomic data. He will be the primary maintainer for the `atomic` and other subpackages, and play a leading role in maintaining and updating tests and documentation throughout the package. He will coordinate official releases of PlasmaPy, along with the rest of PlasmaPy's Coordinating Committee. He will serve as PlasmaPy's representative to the Python in Heliophysics Community (PyHC) with the goal of including PlasmaPy as a well-integrated component in the emerging Python ecosystem for heliophysics. Dr. Murphy, who recently became certified as a Software Carpentry instructor, will co-lead Software Carpentry workshops and provide tutorials on how to use and contribute to PlasmaPy. He will provide support to new users and contributors. He will organize the PlasmaPy workshop and work week in years 1 & 5 and will advise a summer student intern in years 2 & 4.

Dr. Tulasi Parashar will be responsible for implementing time-series turbulence analysis tools into PlasmaPy and developing the dispersion relation solver. He will advise students and continue to serve on PlasmaPy's Coordinating Committee. He will lead tutorials on how to use and contribute to PlasmaPy and support new users and contributors. He will organize the PlasmaPy workshop and work week in year 2.

Dr. Erik Everson will lead code development for experimental analysis tools and determine which experimental analysis code development tasks to prioritize based on community feedback. He will coordinate with different experiments and laboratories, including the Basic Plasma Science Facility (BaPSF). He will be primarily responsible for developing tools to access remote plasma data sets as those data sets become available. He will maintain and update tests and documentation throughout the package. He will lead tutorials on how to use and contribute to PlasmaPy, advise students, and support new users and contributors. He will have primary responsibility to organize the PlasmaPy workshop and work week in year 3.

Dr. David Schaffner will support Dr. Everson in developing experimental analysis tools and will coordinate PlasmaPy development with different experimental efforts at small colleges. He will advise multiple students throughout the project and will organize the

PlasmaPy workshop and work week in year 4. He will be responsible for coordinating travel support for external students attending PlasmaPy workshops for all years.

Dr. Steve Vincena will support Dr. Everson and Dr. Schaffner in planning and developing experimental analysis tools, coordinating with different experiments, and advising students.

Collaborators **Dominik Stańczak** and **Andrew Leonard** will fulfill their responsibilities as PlasmaPy Coordination Committee members, as described below.

Collaborator **Troy Carter** will provide sample experimental data and coordinate with the proposal team on incorporating BaPSF analysis software into the software ecosystem being developed in this proposal.

We have budgeted for consultation services during every year of this project. We will consult with Julia Computing as necessary for assistance with software design, code reviews, parallelization and performance engineering. We will consult with WebAIM and other organizations as necessary for support in improving disability access in the PlasmaPy community, accurate captioning of videos to be posted online, and American Sign Language (ASL) interpretation during workshops (if requested).

2. Project Management

A sustainable open source project requires a robust organizational structure. PlasmaPy's organizational structure is based on the practices of established, successful projects such as [Astropy](#) and [SunPy](#).

The defining documents for the PlasmaPy project are [PlasmaPy Enhancement Proposals \(PLEPs\)](#). A **standard PLEP** introduces and describes a major change to the PlasmaPy code base, such as a new feature or subpackage, major refactoring of an existing subpackage, or a backwards incompatible change. A standard PLEP will start out as a proposal and eventually evolve into a design document if accepted. A **process PLEP** describes a new process or change to an existing process in the management and coordination of PlasmaPy. Examples include changes to PlasmaPy decision-making processes or management structure, guidelines, or procedures. Accepted process PLEPs describe the governance of PlasmaPy. An **informational PLEP** provides information to the broader PlasmaPy community. PLEPs are openly archived on Zenodo. The purposes and guidelines of PLEPs are defined in [PLEP 1](#). PLEPs provide an opportunity for all members of the plasma physics community to substantially influence the direction of PlasmaPy and affiliated packages.

PlasmaPy's Coordinating Committee oversees and manages project activities. The responsibilities of the Coordinating Committee are described in [PLEP 2](#), and are to ensure that necessary roles are being filled; coordinate and delegate tasks; facilitate community-wide communication; oversee code development; manage the PlasmaPy

repositories; regulate intercompatibility; seek funding mechanisms; coordinate grant proposals; facilitate compromises and cooperation; enforce the code of conduct; and foster a culture of appreciation. The Coordinating Committee is responsible for making official decisions on PLEPs after a period of community input and discussion. To promote long-term software sustainability, PlasmaPy will apply to become an affiliated project of [NumFOCUS](#) with the longer-term goal of becoming a sponsored project.

3. Communication Mechanisms

PlasmaPy has multiple communication channels to facilitate code development and other project activities. Informal day-to-day communication is achieved using [Matrix](#), an open source protocol for text-based chat that can be bridged to other chat platforms such as [Gitter](#) and [Slack](#). We will continue to hold informal biweekly community meetings using the open source [Jitsi](#) web-based video conferencing platform. Minutes are collectively taken and stored using Google Docs. We will use Jitsi to hold online tutorials and code review sessions. Announcements and occasional discussion take place using the PlasmaPy email list. We will continue to use GitHub's project management features such as issues and projects to coordinate code development activities.

4. Meetings and Workshops

We will organize a PlasmaPy workshop and work week during each year of the proposal. This gathering will include tutorials on using and contributing to PlasmaPy, informal talks, roadmap planning discussions, and time for code development and working on other action items that arose over the course of the week. We will invite members of the broader plasma physics community, including representatives from different groups and experiments. The workshops and work weeks will be held at SAO in Cambridge, MA in years 1 & 5; the University of Delaware in Newark, DE in year 2; UCLA in Los Angeles, CA in year 3; and Bryn Mawr College near Philadelphia, PA in year 4. The budget for each institution includes travel for members of the proposal team and students to travel to workshops held at other institutions. The budget for Bryn Mawr College includes travel funding for 2, 4, 6, 8, & 10 external students to attend the PlasmaPy workshop and work week in years 1–5, respectively. The year 1 budget for SAO includes funding to bring Coordinating Committee members from Europe to the inaugural workshop. We anticipate that these workshops will grow in size from ~10–15 people in year 1 to potentially ≥ 35 people year 5. By the end of this project, we intend for these gatherings to evolve into annual Python in Plasma Physics workshops akin to the Python in Astronomy workshops that have been happening since 2015. The schedule for these workshops will be inspired by the schedules for [Python in Astronomy](#) and [AstroHackWeek](#) as guides.

We will hold a PlasmaPy workshop or event each year alongside the [American Physical Society \(APS\) Division of Plasma Physics \(DPP\)](#) conference. We will use these meetings to coordinate code development and other activities. We may include tutorials on how to use and contribute to PlasmaPy. The budgets for each institution allow for project participants and students to attend this meeting as well as the APS DPP conference, and conference room rental is in the SAO budget. The scheduling of this workshop will depend on team member availability. We will avoid overlap with the student day that is expected to be held before each DPP meeting starting in 2019. In some years, we may propose a mini-conference, tutorial talk, and/or town hall.

The [PlasmaPy Community Code of Conduct](#) will apply to all of these meetings and workshops. We will distribute the Code of Conduct to all attendees prior to the meeting and post it prominently at each meeting.

Data Management Plan

1. Research Products

The main research products of this project will be the **code and documentation of PlasmaPy and affiliated packages**. We will additionally create research products including but not necessarily limited to **presentations, journal articles, and tutorials**. We may use or create **datasets** for tutorials, testing, calibration, and functionality needed by users (e.g., atomic data). PlasmaPy research products have been and shall always be released under permissive licenses to maximize the potential for use, modification, dissemination, and scientific reproducibility.

2. Licensing

PlasmaPy is being developed openly on GitHub under the [BSD 3-clause license](#) with the explicit patent grant from the [Open Source Initiative \(OSI\)](#) approved [BSD+Patent license](#). This license is permissive and does not restrict redistribution or modification. In contrast to copyleft licenses, the BSD license permits relicensing and allows proprietary derivative works. Software released under a BSD license may be combined with code released under permissive open source licenses, copyleft licenses, and proprietary licenses. The patent grant explicitly permits the use, modification, and redistribution of the source code even if a contributor later patents their contribution. Including a patent grant is important because of the potential for commercial applications. This license thus provides users with more rights and protections than the traditional [BSD 2-clause](#) and BSD 3-clause licenses. This choice maximizes license compatibility with Astropy, SunPy, NumPy, and SciPy.

Publications, presentations, and other research products associated with PlasmaPy will be made openly available under [Creative Commons](#) licenses. We will use the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International \(CC BY 4.0\) license](#) for most of these research products. This license allows redistribution and modification of the creative work if attribution is provided. We will infrequently release research products under other licenses, such as the copyleft [Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International \(CC BY-SA 4.0\) license](#), when necessary for license compatibility. In some instances, we may release research products under the [Creative Commons Universal Public Domain Dedication \(CC0 1.0\)](#). Some works such as tutorials will contain code as well as narrative text. In these cases, the code will generally be released under the BSD+Patent license while the associated text will be released under the CC BY 4.0 license.

3. Versioning

PlasmaPy has adopted the [Semantic Versioning \(SemVer\) 2.0.0 standard \(Preston-Werner 2013\)](#). Version numbers are given by $x.y.z$ where x , y , and z are the major, minor, and patch numbers, respectively. The $0.y.z$ series corresponds to development releases, for which the application programming interface (API) is assumed to be unstable. Starting with version 1.0.0, backward incompatible changes will only be allowed when the major release number is incremented. Minor releases indicate backward compatible expansion of functionality. Patch releases indicate bug fixes and changes that do not affect the API. The primary advantage of SemVer is that version number changes are clearly defined according to an established standard so that users can know if an upgrade indicates loss of backward compatibility. Further detail on changes will be recorded in the PlasmaPy change log and release notes. The history of code development and the reasoning behind decisions are contained in the commit log as well as GitHub issues and pull requests.

4. Availability

We will openly archive most of our research products on [Zenodo](#) under the licenses described above. Datasets will be archived on Zenodo and/or made available on [GitHub's Large File Storage \(LFS\) site](#). Test data will generally be downsampled to reduce file size and computing time and then included directly in the PlasmaPy repository. Large test datasets such as calibration data from experiments will be archived on Zenodo or LFS, as appropriate. We will openly archive the Project Description, References, Data Management Plan, Management and Coordination Plan, and Delivery Mechanism and Community Usage Metrics sections of this proposal on Zenodo under the terms of the CC BY 4.0 license. We will investigate adding tools such as [ReproZip](#) (Chirigati et al. 2016) that enable computational reproducibility into the PlasmaPy workflow. Several of these tools are currently under development.

5. Compliance

Our proposed activities might include a survey to request feedback from the plasma physics community about the future development of PlasmaPy. The survey will not ask for any private personally identifiable information. We will consult the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the appropriate host institution(s) on the chance that IRB approval will be required.

We will periodically consult the export compliance officer for the Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory to verify that planned code development is not subject to export control.

Delivery Mechanism and Community Usage Metrics

1. Deliverables and services

The primary deliverables of this project are the **official releases of PlasmaPy and affiliated packages** with associated **documentation**. Secondary deliverables include **journal articles, presentations, technical reports, tutorials, guides**, and [PlasmaPy Enhancement Proposals \(PLEPs\)](#). Some **datasets** may be created or compiled for testing or demonstration purposes. The primary services to be provided include **user/developer support, trainings, tutorials**, and [Software Carpentry workshops](#).

2. Delivery mechanisms

Official releases of PlasmaPy and affiliated Python packages will be made available on the [Python Package Index \(PyPI\)](#) for standard installation with `pip` and on [conda-forge](#) for installation with the conda package manager. Releases of any Julia packages will be made available through `conda-forge` and [Julia's built-in package manager](#). We will make official releases available via additional suitable package managers as appropriate.

Development of PlasmaPy is open. Users will continue to have access to the development versions of PlasmaPy and affiliated packages by viewing, forking, or cloning the open repositories. Users may access the development history of PlasmaPy via the commit log which may be accessed using `git` and GitHub.

Online documentation for all official releases and the latest version on GitHub will continue to be hosted using Read the Docs at <http://docs.plasmapy.org/>.

Journal articles will be published using open access options (e.g., the *Author Select* option for *Physics of Plasmas*) to avoid financial barriers to access to this information.

Official releases; presentation slides for conferences, workshops, and seminars; technical reports; tutorials; guides; PLEPs; and important data sets will be permanently openly archived on [Zenodo](#) and assigned [Digital Object Identifiers \(DOIs\)](#). Records on Zenodo may be versioned. Each version of a record is assigned a unique DOI, and a “concept” DOI is assigned to represent all versions of the record. Records placed on Zenodo are findable through the “PlasmaPy Community” at <https://zenodo.org/communities/plasmapy/>.

3. Metrics to assess development and delivery of services

We will quantitatively assess the development of core and affiliated packages by using usage statistics on GitHub across repositories such as the frequency of commits, the frequencies that issues are raised or resolved, and the frequencies that pull requests

are being proposed or merged. Changes to code can have vastly different difficulties (ranging from trivial to walking into Mordor), so these frequencies should be treated as rough proxies. Based on Astropy's development history, we anticipate a few thousand commits, a few hundred issues raised/resolved, and a few hundred pull requests proposed/merged per year for an actively developed project.

We will qualitatively assess development by determining whether or not the most pressing capabilities are being created, bugs are being fixed, documentation is being written and kept up-to-date, pull requests are being reviewed, new code is readable and maintainable, and the test suite is thorough and meets code quality standards.

We will quantitatively assess delivery of services by the frequency of major and minor releases of the PlasmaPy core package. At the beginning of the project, our target will be at least one release every ≤ 8 months. At the end of the project, our target will be at least one release every ≤ 5 months.

3.1. Metrics for assessing community adoption and usage

A goal for this project is to develop a group of core contributors that extends beyond the proposal team. We will use the mean number of unique contributors per month as a metric for the strength of the contributor base. Our targets are for this number to be 6, 8, 10, 12, and 14 per month at the end of the five years of this project, respectively. We will use the number of contributors who have made more than 100 commits to the project as a gauge of broader community participation. Our targets for this number to be 7, 9, 11, 13, and 15 by the end of each of the five years of this project. The final values were chosen to be comparable to the corresponding values for SunPy. We will create a log-log plot at the end of each year for the number of commits as a function of number of committers (e.g., [Astropy Collaboration et al. 2018](#)) as a visual metric.

We will use the rate of downloads of different versions of PlasmaPy from PyPI to gauge community usage. This metric requires calibration as users may download PlasmaPy multiple times. We will use the data from the first year and the earliest releases as baselines so that we can calculate the relative change for subsequent years. Our target is to increase the rate of downloads by $\sim 25\%$ each year.

We will similarly measure the changes in number of citations and acknowledgments to PlasmaPy research products, with the caveat that it is less common to cite or acknowledge software in plasma physics literature than in astronomy.

Reviews of Proposal from NSF

Panel Summary

Summary:

This proposal seeks to create an ecosystem within the plasma science community recognizing the benefits of this in the astrophysics community. The proposal aims to build a community-based infrastructure that is needed and that various institutions, including small colleges and programs, can benefit from. The tools include theory, simulation, and experimental software infrastructure that can support plasma science and experiments.

Intellectual Merit

Strengths

- The proposal is founded upon building a community and realizing that a sustainable and accessible infrastructure needs to be built to meet community needs
- Plasma physics simulations draw on many components of science and the team understands that having one package that combines the fragmented pieces of software has significant benefits
- The proposal makes a clear case of explicit community interest in developing this
- The infrastructure reduces duplication and time wasted by students and early career scientists in re-implementing things as opposed to gaining educational benefits aimed at furthering science
- There is a clear plan to document everything and a clear idea to test software and work out any bugs
- Simulations of small experiments and Langmuir probe data are provided as examples of real world scientific questions that this tool can help study and address.

Weaknesses

- An important question to directly address is what science can/cannot be done without this infrastructure.

Broader Impacts

Strengths

- The educational and outreach components of this proposal have very high value as the broader impacts and community building efforts are very strong in this proposal

- This proposal is written clearly highlighting community requests for such a tool and is responsive to the theory, simulation, and experimental components broadly

Weaknesses

-

CSSI Specific Review Criteria:

Science-driven:

Strengths

- Such an infrastructure will be very useful for advancing science in research and also for education through modular parallel code that allows integration of new models and enables new science with performance and model improvements that can be made by the community

Weaknesses

- The scientific output is not directly evident through science-motivating questions that the infrastructure will address

Innovation:

Strengths

- Using Jupyter notebooks and Julia is an innovative approach to education and research

Weaknesses

-

Close collaborations among stakeholders:

Strengths

- The team is very strong and has complementary expertise to perform the research proposed

Weaknesses

-

Building on existing, recognized capabilities:

Strengths

- PlasmaPy already exists as a relatively new package and has engaged a large number of users including some who have contributed to code development

Weaknesses

-

Project plans, and system and process architecture:

Strengths

- The project and management plans are strong.

Weaknesses

-

Deliverables:

Strengths

- The deliverables include open-source software, a sustainable community of developers and users, and support. These are clearly articulated in the proposal.

Weaknesses

-

Metrics:

Strengths

- The metrics are clearly outlined with targets included for each year.

Weaknesses

-

Sustained and sustainable impacts:

Strengths

- The proposers present an excellent sustainability plan that relies on community development and use. There is a clear indication of community interest in the proposal to sustain this infrastructure.

Weaknesses

-

Alignment with Directorate Specific Priorities:

Strengths

- This proposal aims to provide a much needed unified software infrastructure in the plasma physics community.

Weaknesses

-

Data Management Plan:

The data management plan is adequate.

Post Doc Mentoring Plan:

Not applicable

Suggestions for Improvement:

The panel suggests highlighting some important scientific questions that this infrastructure can enable so the scientific output is evident. The proposers have provided Langmuir probe analysis as an example but it is helpful to build on that to address important scientific questions.

Summary Statement

The panel agrees that this is an excellent proposal that has a good likelihood of success. This proposal clearly responds to the CSSI call, proposing metrics, deliverables and describes a clear path to sustainability, making it truly stand out as responding to the CSSI call. This proposal meets a critical need of building community around open source models in plasma science. On top of the critical need for community, this proposal also builds critically needed infrastructure for the plasma science community. The panel noted that while this is exactly what the community needs, there needs to be a scientific focus for the team in order to drive development. For example, having one or two key experiments the team is modeling to enable the understanding of basic physics or give insight into a key application would greatly focus the coding effort and the team. Spending at least a couple of pages on this in the proposal would have really strengthened the proposal. While the reviewers acknowledge simulating Langmuir probes is a hard problem, because of getting all the physics right at the boundaries and the possibility of double layers and the impact of collision physics on the results, it's not clear what if any of the physics challenges will be explored in the very brief description the PIs give. This also prevents the code base from becoming unbounded in scope, due to the large number of models there are in plasmas. The idea of a driving example is needed to set metrics and drive the effort forward, the panel felt that the general open framework that is proposed is clearly what is needed in the community.

Recommendation: Highly Competitive

The panelists concur that the panel summary accurately reflects the panel discussion

PANEL RECOMMENDATION: Highly Competitive

Proposal Review 1

Rating:

Excellent

Summary

In the context of the five review elements, please evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the proposal with respect to intellectual merit.

This proposal is clearly from people who have code which solves real problems and which has reached the point in its evolution where work on the infrastructure is necessary for continued advancement of its capabilities.

In the context of the five review elements, please evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the proposal with respect to broader impacts.

These are people who know what they are doing and present a clear case for how and why their infrastructure must be improved for further sustained development. I have not doubt that they will accomplish this and that the code will continue to address the many areas of research discussed in the proposal.

Please evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the proposal with respect to any additional solicitation-specific review criteria, if applicable

Both the goals and details of the proposed work are very clearly presented. Even though the software project I lead is in a different area of simulation, I recognize many similarities to the issues I have had to address. For example, they recognize the critical connection between modularity and organization of the code and allowing implementation of new features without disrupting existing parallelization. This type of consideration reflects experience with code used by a large community of users and developed over a substantial period of time. Similarly, their description of an evolutionary process for software, including periodic restructuring, rather than a "lets throw everything away and start over" approach reflects experience with a user base that cares about getting their work done rather than abstract ideas about how software should be done.

Summary Statement

This is by far the best proposal of the ones I was assigned to read. The wealth of specific goals and detailed plans reflect a completely different level of experience and practicality.

Proposal Review 2

Rating:

Excellent

Summary

In the context of the five review elements, please evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the proposal with respect to intellectual merit.

Strengths

- Open source framework open to community-wide development and input can promote scientific reproducibility, this is the key contribution of the proposed work. Having a unified framework as the one proposed is needed in the plasma physics community and is synergistic with several similar efforts that are being developed.
- The use of Julia for high performance computing coupled with a Python interface is a novel approach in plasma physics. Python has been extensively interfaced with plasma physics codes written in C/C++/Fortran but Julia adds a novel component to this effort. Julia will allow plasma physicists, who are typically not trained as computer scientists, to develop readable code and overcome the significant overhead (many years) of scalable development of new software.
- Including computational and experimental components of such open source development is of very broad appeal and could aid significant scientific advancements for a number of applications in plasma physics
- The team is highly qualified to conduct this research as is evidenced by past performance on NSF grants and publications. Resources are adequate.

Weaknesses

- The proposers cite a reference for the scalability of Julia to petascale, but it is not clear that Julia will scale better than C for the very large computations that are necessary for most applications in plasma physics. Perhaps this requires some exploration/experimentation before the commitment is made to write the core pieces of code in Julia.

In the context of the five review elements, please evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the proposal with respect to broader impacts.

Strengths

- The broader impacts include a strong educational component. Student advising, access to newcomers to the field, an open source development software with significant community input, workshops and tutorials, accessible development to

students and scientists with disabilities are all exceptionally strong contributors to broader impacts. The aim of this proposal is to support theory, simulation, and experimental efforts in a variety of plasma physics areas to include a wide variety of laboratory and space applications.

Please evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the proposal with respect to any additional solicitation-specific review criteria, if applicable

Science-driven:

Strengths

- By enabling a community development of an open source tool, the potential for scientific advancement is significant. In addition to providing a framework for research, a possibly more significant impact is through education. Having an easy to use, open source, reproducible tool for students has the potential to provide the community with workforce that can further the scientific field by building on existing platforms versus starting new development which is often the case. This proposal aims to benefit the plasma physics community beyond the initial participants.

Weaknesses

- It is recommended to connect with existing codes and developers of other software outside of the key developers of this collaboration to ensure that the tools being developed in this unified system are well-benchmarked for both accuracy and scalability

Innovation:

Strengths

- The work aims to build a plasma physics ecosystem for the community, which is much needed particularly for institutions that are developing new plasma physics programs. Promising effort to lay the foundation for an accessible framework that the community can build on. Human and technical aspects are considered through the choice of programming languages, ease of use, sophisticated testing platforms, flexible frameworks to enable a wide variety of problems, and even accessibility considerations for individuals with disabilities.

Close collaborations among stakeholders:

Strengths

- The partnerships and community development efforts are very strong. The proposal actively engages input from diverse communities and institutions to enable access to a broad community of students, early career researchers, small colleges, and also larger laboratories and facilities. Also, developers with

substantially diverse expertise across multiple institutions are engaged in the proposal.

Building on existing, recognized capabilities:

Strengths

- PlasmaPy v0.1.1 already exists and has engaged 83 members including a number of them who have contributed to the code development. So this proposal leverages an existing framework.

Project plans, and system and process architecture:

Strengths

- Management plan is well outlined and there is a clear mechanism to share results through publications, tutorials, workshops, online community engagement, etc. Project plan is robust.

Deliverables:

Strengths

- The deliverable, which is an open-source tool aimed at reproducibility and ease of use, is much needed and has the potential for high impact in the plasma physics community. A unified framework that can enable scientific impact in computation, theory, and experiment is needed and this proposal aims to deliver such a framework. There is a github repository available for public access. Also included in the deliverables are documentation, reports, tutorials, guides, datasets, user support, trainings, workshops, and engagement of diverse, under-represented individuals including those with disabilities.

Metrics:

Strengths

- The metrics to measure success will be done through monitoring GitHub commits, issues raised/resolved, pull requests, frequency of releases of the package, measuring the average number of contributors each month, measuring the number of downloads of the package to gauge community usage. Each of these will be tracked each year of the project. These means will provide sufficient data to gauge the usage and success of the project. The metrics are clear and effective.

Sustained and sustainable impacts:

Strengths

- The very foundations of this work are to develop and establish a widely accessible long-term community infrastructure for plasma physics in theory, simulation, and experiment. This aspect of the proposal is very strong and there is no doubt, that if such a unified framework were to be successfully created and generally applied, there would be sustainable impact.

Summary Statement

In summary, this proposal is excellent, timely, and much needed in the plasma physics community. It is highly responsive to a call on infrastructure development. It is an ambitious proposal aiming to incorporate a plasma physics ecosystem for theory, simulation, and experiment and also multiple different simulation models (fluid, PIC, etc.) and experimental diagnostics. This appears to be fairly high risk because of the large extent that it spans, but has significant potential for high reward if successful. There is a clear outline of how the proposers will engage the community, including reaching out to a diverse audience, and encouraging ease of access, reproducibility, community input to produce a novel tool that can support small and large, computational and experimental programs at various institutions. There is a strong educational component motivating this work. There is also a clear plan on the deliverables and metrics for each year with a lot of room for modifications and updates depending on how the project evolves and community input. An important suggestion that could strengthen this effort is to connect with existing codes and developers of other software to ensure that the tools being developed in this unified system are well-benchmarked and compare with previous results for accuracy, scalability, etc. That being said, the broader impacts are excellent, the potential for scientific advancement in plasma physics longer-term is significant, and the team is highly qualified to carry out the proposed work.

Proposal Review 3

Rating:

Very Good

Summary

In the context of the five review elements, please evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the proposal with respect to intellectual merit.

Strengths

- The work is nicely detailed and well thought out in terms of software development plans, choice of programming constructs and data structures, and general approach to having an extensible and sustainable open-source community-based software. The software will help make more of plasma physics simulations and analysis available for a broader plasma science community in the form of documented open source software, to help incoming students quickly get up to speed, and reduce duplication of effort and data conversion. It will accelerate the research work of others in the community.

Weaknesses

- There are no new scientific methods or investigations proposed. Namely, only known and existing computational, theoretical, or software platforms are to be integrated, documented, and coalesced into a single software base. This is therefore purely a software and community effort, with zero scientific or methodological advance for plasma physics directly being implemented, tried out, or incorporated or examined. It was a rather odd omission. This is really a software project in the narrow sense.

In the context of the five review elements, please evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the proposal with respect to broader impacts.

Strengths

- The broad impact could be very strong. If this works well and is adopted by the plasma physics community, it will enhance collaboration, reduce redundant work, wastes of time converting proprietary data formats, and help on-board new students and incorporate their later methodological contributions into a single software base for the community. Diversity and inclusivity are explicitly addressed and taken very seriously.

Weaknesses

- Not any that are truly obvious.

Please evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the proposal with respect to any additional solicitation-specific review criteria, if applicable

Science-driven:

Strengths

- This enables great science by others hopefully and in a broad sense.

Weaknesses

- No new science is proposed or investigated directly by this effort of so many experts.

Innovation:

Strengths

- The latest and greatest ideas for software development are applied. This is somewhat innovative in the sense that the standards of the field are so low that 'the one-eyed man is king'.

Weaknesses

- Everything proposed is known already or demonstrated to work by others, so in this sense it is not as innovative.

Close collaborations among stakeholders:

Strengths

- The PIs will work closely and are representative of different branches of the field.

Weaknesses

- None noted.

Building on existing, recognized capabilities:

Strengths

- The PIs already have a software starting base, already had it developed via a (small) community effort, and have apparent buy-in from many, many PIs in their field. This is all already done. They have demonstrated working software already and plan to convert and extend it.

Weaknesses

- None noted.

Project plans, and system and process architecture:

Strengths

- The plan for software development is sensible and starts correctly by building good foundations.

Weaknesses

- None noted.

Deliverables:

Strengths

- Deliverables are clear: software, software packages, and workshops.

Weaknesses

- None noted.

Metrics:

Strengths

- Standard fare: count users, downloads, contributions. Nothing exciting nor problematic.

Weaknesses

- None noted

Sustained and sustainable impacts:

Strengths

- This could turn out to be a sustainable effort as they have documented many students and PIs in their field publishing requests, works, and software frameworks for a cohesive project of this sort. There will thus be a small community from the get-go that will be very interested in this project and using its output.

Weaknesses

- This will depend on who uses the software: if other people use it to do science, there will be sustainable impact. All this project can do is help them get out of the door more quickly and efficiently.

Summary Statement

This proposal aims to significantly develop PlasmaPy (python based software) for plasma physics broadly incorporating core functionality for all users and then specialized packages as additions. The aim is to incorporate established methods,

develop standards for data, aid experimental analysis, and accelerate incoming students into plasma research.

This is a very good proposal. The potential impact on the subfield will be very strong, broad, and there is already community demand that is documented for this type of project. The plans for the software package and development are detailed, modern, and sensible. The outreach is strong and sensible. The only negative aspect is the lack of actual scientific or technological advances by this project itself: the PIs aim to make a wonderful software framework incorporating known and tested approaches from various areas to advance the pace of research in plasma science, but the proposal itself doesn't provide any plans for scientific advancement per se.

Proposal Review 4

Rating:

Excellent

Summary

In the context of the five review elements, please evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the proposal with respect to intellectual merit.

Strengths

Because of the very large number of models needed to describe the full range of plasma physics, there does not exist a single validated community code base for plasmas. Within the last 15 years, a few open source community codes have emerged as very successful at pushing the astronomy part of the science forwards, eg, ENZO, YT, Astropy, etc. This proposal targets creating a code ecosystem in an easy to devolve paradigm (Python/Julia) for supporting a range of efforts related to a host of new small experimental facilities cropping up at a number of small universities. In plasmas, simulations are a key tool used to understand much of what is measured in experiments. The codes will be easy to use with documentation created in Jupyter notebooks. A huge amount of research has gone into understanding how to create and grow community code bases for longevity, and this team understands and intends to follow best practices in creating an open source community code. The goal is the fostering of the community to meet the growing needs of simulation support at smaller experimental facilities at smaller institution. The team has a clear commitment to the values of open source and easily maintainable community code.

Weaknesses

This is an important but big project. Would be nice to see them focus on 3 or 4 experimental facilities as a way to start.

In the context of the five review elements, please evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the proposal with respect to broader impacts.

Strengths

This effort will lead to tools that can be used for teaching in the class room. Through the development of these tools, it clearly support scientific efforts at smaller institutions. It creates opportunity for scientific outreach by bringing visualization and simulation to the whole community.

Weaknesses

No weakness

Please evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the proposal with respect to any additional solicitation-specific review criteria, if applicable

Science-driven:

Strengths

This targets support of the plasma science community as a whole. Starting by targeting the simulations of basic measurement devices such as Langmuir probes for plasmas, they are directly contenting with what the experimentalists use to explore their systems. The team is working towards building models of devices used in measurement.

Weaknesses

No weakness

Innovation:

Strengths

The team has clearly presented that they know how to build a CI eco-system that will sustain these ideas long after this project is no longer funded. By targeting easy to maintain scalable computing paradigms, such as Julia, they have put real thought into the choices they need to consider for the infrastructure side of the ecosystem by keeping the entry easy while permitting complex capabilities. The model for code review, and the emphasis on keeping down technical debt was nice to see.

Weaknesses

The choice on doing all simulations implicit seemed like an unnecessary complication for a community code starting out.

Close collaborations among stakeholders:

Strengths

This clear fosters partnerships to build a CI community. Builds this within the plasma physics community.

Weaknesses

The team does not currently connect with Engineers or other sciences who are in this community. It looks like they know how, but it is not demonstrated.

Building on existing, recognized capabilities:

Strengths

The PlasmaPy just released 2.0. They are about 4 years old.

Weaknesses

Github shows about 9 regular contributors (45 total) who were all busy with a fluey of activity for version 2.0. They are still working on things like documentation.

Project plans, and system and process architecture:

Strengths

Has a strong management plan with regular code review to reduce technical debt. Further, they have developed rules of engagement for emerging people to contribute and become valued members of the team.

Weaknesses

No weakness

Deliverables:

Strengths

The services are clear, support for the simulation of experiments and tools for exploring plasmas. Building the open source community is as important as most aspects of this change.

Weaknesses

No weakness

Metrics:

Strengths

The team has a moderate to aggressive time line they have presented as part of their management plan. They do have a time line and metrics for the base code.

Weaknesses

Why the team has clearly expanded how to build community, they did not explain metrics for build community.

Sustained and sustainable impacts:

Strengths

Clearly the team understands the build community is how they will create a stable ecosystem. The proposal really is about how to do this well.

Weaknesses

No weakness

Alignment with Directorate Specific Priorities:

Strengths

This adds a lot of value to the plasma physics community. This one of the things that is missing.

Weaknesses

No weakness

Data Management Plan:

The data management plan was well written. They are using Github for propagation for software produced and maintainability.

Post Doc Mentoring Plan:

N/A

Suggestions for Improvement:

Improving the proposal would involve engaging more of the community: nuclear, mechanical or electrical engineering.

Summary Statement

The proposal will clearly fill and important need within the plasma physics community by creating an open source easy to maintain plasmas simulation framework targeting modeling of explements.

Clarifications to CSSI Proposal⁴

Nicholas Murphy, David Schaffner, Tulasi Parashar, Steve Vincena, & Erik Everson

July 15, 2019

The document contains the requested clarifications on the proposal, “Collaborative Research: Frameworks: An open source software ecosystem for plasma physics” that was submitted to NSF’s Cyberinfrastructure for Sustained Scientific Innovation (CSSI) program. We are grateful for the opportunity to address the questions that have arisen during the review process.

1. If you think there is any perception of overlap between this project and other funded work, please explain how this project will differ from other funded work.

Dr. Vincena is a co-PI of a grant to support UCLA’s Basic Plasma Science Facility (BaPSF). BaPSF has only 0.5 FTE dedicated for all of its IT needs. This includes maintenance and development of its data acquisition system; a separate computerized system to monitor and control operations of the Large Plasma Device; and basic data analysis software, such as its recently released `bapsflib` Python package. This package is dedicated to reading data and collating metadata stored in the facility’s HDF5 data files. Development of a separate package akin to PlasmaPy was discussed as being extremely useful for data analysis, but could not be achieved without sacrificing mission-critical resources needed to maintain and improve the facility’s current software infrastructure.

Dr. Murphy’s work on PlasmaPy through version 0.2.0 was supported as a broader impacts component of a DOE grant awarded through the NSF/DOE Partnership in Basic Plasma Science and Engineering. This grant will be ending shortly. None of the other grants led or co-led by members of the proposal team include any support for code development of PlasmaPy.

Can you elaborate on the software development process used to develop the framework? What SE focused approaches will be used? Which of the PI team will be responsible for the SE process?

The overarching software engineering process for PlasmaPy is the open development model used by projects such as Astropy. In the open development model, anyone who follows the code of conduct may contribute to PlasmaPy. The strength of this model is

⁴ This component of the document includes responses to questions raised by the NSF program manager prior to the proposal was recommended for funding. The proposal team did not have access to the panel summary and proposal reviews while these responses were being prepared.

that it builds a community of user-developers. The challenge of this model is that new contributors may be unfamiliar with software engineering techniques. We will introduce new contributors to version control with git and GitHub, continuous integration testing, and constructive code review as they are making their first pull requests. As they gain experience, we will introduce test-driven development, code coverage testing, and other techniques used by core developers. PlasmaPy's online documentation contains a development guide that describes our practices.

When developing a subpackage, we will collect potential use cases from plasma researchers and educators and apply them to create a software requirements specification in the form of a PlasmaPy Enhancement Proposal (PLEP). The use cases will help us define a suitable application programming interface. Dr. Murphy is writing a PLEP with use cases and a software requirements specification for this framework's simulation capabilities, and Dr. Everson will lead this effort for `plasmapy.diagnostics`.

The software engineering community has largely converged on agile software development, though most of the agile techniques are designed for commercial rather than scientific applications. We will use agile techniques to the extent that they apply to scientific software development. There are many different flavors of agile programming, and we must pick one that is compatible with the open development model. We will use Kanban because it is conceptually simple, suitable for geographically separated teams, and non-hierarchical. PlasmaPy's Coordinating Committee (which currently includes Dr. Murphy and Dr. Parashar) will oversee the software development process. Dr. Murphy, Dr. Parashar, and Dr. Everson will share direct responsibility for the software engineering processes for the activities described in our proposal. We will continue our practice of regularly reflecting on how our team can become more effective and change our processes in response.

Please re-state the software license(s) that will be used in your project and justify your choice(s).

PlasmaPy is openly available under the terms of the Open Source Initiative (OSI) approved BSD+Patent license. We chose a permissive license to maximize license compatibility and allow PlasmaPy to be used, modified, and redistributed under the same or a different license with essentially no restrictions. In particular, the BSD+Patent license is two-way compatible with each of the BSD 2-clause or 3-clause licenses used by Astropy and SunPy. In contrast, copyleft licenses are often only one-way compatible with permissive licenses.

A known limitation of the BSD 2-clause and 3-clause licenses is that they lack protections against software patents. A contributor could potentially contribute to a

package, patent their contribution, and then prohibit the package from using their contribution. The BSD+Patent license contains an explicit patent grant that gives users the right to keep using all contributions to the package even if a contributor patents their contribution. This clause is potentially important because plasma physics has extensive commercial applications.

Can you provide more details on the community engagement? Any specific activities that will show that a community of users will be engaged and supported is appreciated. Please clarify the mechanisms you will use to reach out to engage users and/or developers, particularly for other communities in adopting your software. Please be as detailed as possible here.

We will organize a PlasmaPy workshop and work week during each year of the proposal. The gathering will include tutorials on using and contributing to PlasmaPy, informal talks, roadmap planning discussions, and coding sprints. We have requested travel funds to bring students to this meeting. We will advertise these workshops broadly by, for example, submitting items to the newsletter of the American Physical Society (APS) Division of Plasma Physics (DPP). We anticipate that these workshops will evolve into annual Python in Plasma Physics meetings akin to the Python in Astronomy meetings.

It will be of particular importance to engage students, early career scientists, and plasma educators, especially as they have been the strongest source of support for PlasmaPy. We will introduce PlasmaPy through summer schools such as the MIT Computational Physics School for Fusion Research and those run by the APS DPP Topical Group on Plasma Astrophysics. Dr. Murphy will be giving a lunch talk on PlasmaPy at the inaugural MIT summer school in August 2019. Dr. Murphy and Dr. Schaffner have begun discussions with Dr. Arturo Dominguez of the Science Education Department at the Princeton Plasma Physics Laboratory (PPPL) about incorporating PlasmaPy into PPPL's Science Undergraduate Laboratory Internship program, Minority Serving Institution Faculty Workshop in Plasma Physics, and Graduate Summer School in Plasma Physics. Dr. Schaffner will introduce students and educators to PlasmaPy through the Small College Plasma Consortium that he is founding with his recent NSF CAREER award. Dr. Murphy will co-lead Software Carpentry workshops at educational institutions with programs in plasma physics, and conclude with an introduction to PlasmaPy.

We will hold a PlasmaPy workshop or event that is open to the community at the annual APS DPP meeting. This event will not overlap with the newly organized Student Day held just prior to the meeting, though we will offer to coordinate tutorials. We will propose an APS DPP mini-conference on building an open source software ecosystem for plasma physics. Dr. Everson and Dr. Vincena will discuss PlasmaPy at each annual

BaPSF user group meeting. We will present on PlasmaPy at multiple institutions and during multiple conferences each year.

Dr. Murphy will continue engaging with the Python in Heliophysics Community to coordinate code development and interoperability with SunPy, HelioPy, and SpacePy. He is attending the Python in Astronomy workshop this year to promote a partnership with Astropy.

We recently submitted PlasmaPy as an initiative proposal for the APS-DPP Community Planning Process (CPP).⁵ The DPP-CPP provides a unique opportunity to engage with experts in discovery plasma science, magnetic fusion energy (MFE), high energy density physics (HEDP), and fusion materials & technology (FM&T). Dr. Murphy will be attending DPP-CPP workshops to advocate for PlasmaPy, scientific reproducibility, and equity & inclusion in plasma science. Dr. Schaffner and Dr. Vincena will attend as members of the DPP-CPP subcommittee on Discovery Plasma Science and Workforce Development. If our CSSI proposal is awarded by this summer or fall, we will be able to make a much stronger case that the PlasmaPy project be included as a community consensus recommendation in the final report. Having PlasmaPy as a community consensus recommendation will greatly increase the chances of active participation by the MFE and HEDP communities which are primarily funded by DOE. Inclusion in the final report will also improve prospects for long-term software sustainability by opening a door for future DOE funding. We have also submitted papers to the National Academy of Sciences' Decadal Assessment of Plasma Science that advocate for an open source software ecosystem for plasma physics and scientific reproducibility.

Please define community/usage metrics (quantitative metrics are preferred) for each year of the award. These should be simple, but well thought out metrics that will help show what you will accomplish each year and will show the impact of the software on furthering science and the breadth of the user/developer community. For example, metrics that relate to the number of users or research groups, number of citations, number of contributors, etc. For each metric and year also provide specific values. Please be as detailed as possible here.

An essential goal of this project is to develop a group of core contributors that extends beyond the proposal team. We will use the mean number of unique contributors per month and the number of contributors who have made at least 10 pull requests or 100 commits as metrics to gauge the strength of the contributor base. Our targets are 6, 8, 10, 12, and 14 unique contributors per month and 7, 9, 11, 13, and 15 contributors with

⁵ The DPP-CPP began at the request of the DOE Office of Fusion Energy Sciences Advisory Committee (FESAC) with the goal of producing community consensus recommendations for plasma science. These recommendations are to be incorporated into a long-term strategic plan by FESAC that will guide future DOE funding decisions. The DPP-CPP report is to be submitted to FESAC by March 2020.

more than 10 pull requests or 100 commits for years 1–5, respectively. These values were chosen to be comparable to SunPy’s development history. We will create a log-log plot for each year of the number of commits as a function of the number of committers to visually inspect the contributor base.

We will record the number of downloads of PlasmaPy from the Python Package Index (PyPI) and conda-forge to gauge community usage. Data from the first year will provide us with a baseline. Our target is to increase the rate of downloads by at least 25% every year during years 2–5. We will similarly measure the number of citations and acknowledgments to PlasmaPy research products, with the caveat that it is not a particularly common practice in plasma physics research to cite or acknowledge a particular version of software.

We will perform annual community surveys that ask for information on the number of research groups, experimental facilities, and educators who are using or contributing to PlasmaPy. We will use data from year 1 as the baseline and report on the growth of these quantities. In particular, our targets for the number of experimental facilities that are substantially participating in the PlasmaPy project to be 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 in years 1–5, respectively. These surveys will serve as an additional means of community engagement, as we will ask for feature requests, potential use cases, and general feedback for PlasmaPy.

Please provide additional information regarding the critical science that will be enabled by this Framework. The panel expressed concerns that the scientific output is not directly evident through science-motivating questions that the infrastructure will address.

The goal of PlasmaPy is to enable plasma physics students and scientists to investigate a broad range of scientific questions rather than any particular questions. PlasmaPy’s generality is its strength and why it is well-suited for a very broad field such as plasma physics. Since plasma in the universe operates at an enormous number of scales, the number of subfields and specializations are vast as well. This unfortunately naturally leads to the challenge of significant insulation between groups. PlasmaPy aims to bridge these gaps by highlighting commonalities through diagnostics analysis and mathematical approaches that might not otherwise spread through the community. We are designing PlasmaPy to be research software infrastructure that is applicable to a wide variety of research techniques and practices, including but not limited to:

- Analysis of data taken by diagnostics in laboratory plasma experiments.
- Cross-comparisons between results from multiple laboratory experiments (e.g., for data science and/or replicability studies).

- Cross-comparisons between laboratory experiments and numerical simulations (e.g., for validation studies).
- Cross-comparisons between laboratory experiments of varying scale and *in situ* space plasma measurements (to be enabled by working directly with the Python in Heliophysics Community).
- Benchmarks between simulations with different physical models or numerical methods (e.g., for benchmarks, verification studies, and isolating certain physical effects).

Specific science questions will be addressed by affiliated packages that use functionality from the core package and will often be developed by members of the broader plasma physics community. The approach we are proposing will enable PlasmaPy to:

- Shorten development times for experimental, diagnostic, or simulation efforts due to standardization. A consistent approach to probe analysis will lower the hurdle for people to implement new ideas and tweak existing designs.
- Enable students to get off to a running start on their first research projects.
- Diffuse knowledge of analysis techniques and mathematical approaches among different plasma physics subfields. For example, an analysis technique may be used in one area (e.g., space physics) but not in another (e.g., edge turbulence in fusion-relevant experiments), yet if utilized could further development or understanding. Analysis techniques for one subfield could be more clearly made available to plasma physics as a whole through the software ecosystem.
- Improve scientific reproducibility by making analysis software open for inspection, modification, and reuse. Analysis techniques implemented by a particular research group could be made readily available to plasma physics as a whole.
- Shorten the time required to achieve scientific understanding.